

Demographics of Primary Studies

Study ID	Year	Type	Research Classification	Empirical strategie
S01	2016	Conference	Proposal of solution	Case study
S02	2018	Conference	Proposal of solution	Case study
S03	2017	Conference	Validation research	Not described
S04	2016	Conference	Proposal of solution	Not described
S05	2015	Conference	Evaluation research	Case study
S06	2015	Conference	Proposal of solution	Empirical study
S07	2018	Conference	Validation research	Not described
S08	2016	Conference	Evaluation research	Case study
S09	2019	Workshop	Proposal of solution	Not described
S10	2016	Conference	Validation research	Case study
S11	2018	Workshop	Opinion paper	Not described
S12	2018	Conference	Proposal of solution	Experiment
S13	2018	Conference	Validation research	Case study
S14	2018	Conference	Proposal of solution	Experiment
S15	2017	Conference	Proposal of solution	Case study
S16	2017	Journal	Proposal of solution	Case study
S17	2018	Conference	Opinion paper	Not described
S18	2017	Journal	Opinion paper	Survey
S19	2018	Conference	Proposal of solution	Case study
S20	2015	Workshop	Validation research	Experiment
S21	2015	Conference	Validation research	Case study
S22	2019	Conference	Evaluation research	Case study
S23	2019	Conference	Proposal of solution	Case study
S24	2019	Conference	Evaluation research	Not described
S25	2019	Conference	Proposal of solution	Experiment
S26	2019	Conference	Proposal of solution	Experiment
S27	2019	Conference	Proposal of solution	Experiment
S28	2019	Conference	Evaluation research	Experiment
S29	2019	Conference	Evaluation research	Case study
S30	2019	Conference	Proposal of solution	Case study
S31	2019	Journal	Proposal of solution	Experiment